

PARTNERS4LITERACY: A COMPARATIVE CLASSROOM DISCOURSE ANALYSIS DURING
DELIVERY OF READTOPIA INSTRUCTION

by

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Background

Students with complex communication needs (CCN) are often enrolled in special education classrooms and eligible for individualized educational services. The purpose of an individualized education program plan (IEP) is for students with identified speech, language, communication, and learning disabilities to receive a "free appropriate public education (FAPE)" (Individuals with Disabilities Education Act, 2017), as mandated by the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA).

The most recent revision of IDEA (PL 108-446) was passed into national law almost 20 years ago (2004). Despite accumulated evidence suggesting numerous strategic ways to improve students' learning of academic material, the daily applications of many evidence-based instructional strategies in classrooms is unknown or yet to be fully realized (Brady, Bruce, Goldman, Erickson, Mineo, Ogletree, & Wilkinson, 2016; Erickson & Geist, 2016). For example, in 2018, 6.7 million children were served under IDEA, and 14% of all public school students were determined eligible for IEP services under one or more of the 13 identified disability categories (Institute of Educational Sciences, 2021).

Students who are eligible for an IEP consistently perform at a significantly lower reading and math level than their mainstream counterparts in reading and math testing. For example, according to a 2018 National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) report, 63-77% of 12th graders with disabilities scored below a basic level in reading and math (American Institutes for Research, 2018). This high percentage of 12th graders with disabilities who remain at a basic level of math and reading skill at graduation is unfortunate. After all, it was 21 years ago that the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (2000) presented evidence

supporting the need for all children to receive reading instruction and the negative long-term implications of not doing so.

There are alternative and evidence-based ways to test and teach students with special needs, and these alternative testing methods are required under IDEA (National Center on Educational Outcomes, 2015) and part of the Universal Design for Learning (CAST, 2008) framework. Evidence-Based Practices (EBP) that utilize principles of universal design for learning (UDL) are beneficial for students, but research suggests they are not being implemented in classrooms on a large scale (Johnson, Zheng, Crawford, Moylan, 2021). The alternative tests can vary from behavioral assessments to the ways that functional communication can be measured. The different forms of alternative testing are available to teachers and can be used for students with a variety of disabilities.

Special education teachers and speech-language pathologists, here unto labeled as “educators,” report difficulties choosing appropriate assessment measures that realistically identify a nonverbal student’s daily unmet language and literacy needs. Furthermore, many available assessments focus on students’ disabilities or deficits, with single scores that place students on a severity-of-function range but do little to serve as indicators for type or level of instructional need. Although unpacked academic standards and progress benchmarks are readily available as an instructional reference for educators (e.g., Dynamic Learning Maps), not all educators serving students with significant disabilities may use them when constructing goals and measuring progress. Even when adaptable and alternative assessment methods are available, educators may be unaware of how to properly implement them for their students with complex learning needs (Stahmer, Oliver, Schetter, & Stanford University, PACE, 2020). Educators' lack of knowledge and skill in using alternative assessments may hinder appropriate benchmarking

for highlighting student progress. If these published methods are not utilized to assess and teach students with complex communication needs (CCN), then these methods are a wasted resource. Years of published research suggest that students with CCN benefit from comprehensive literacy instruction, but not all special educators are fully implementing these EBP assessments or lessons in their classrooms (Erickson & Koppenhaver, 2020).

At least thirty years of research suggests a link between learning symbolic communication (language) and acquiring literacy (Erickson & Koppenhaver, 2020). Symbolic communication is learned when children begin to put words together, and as children learn to spell. Written communication cannot happen without children knowing their alphabet letters and the sounds the letters represent that ultimately become words. Without teachers who support comprehensive early and emergent literacy instruction that includes essential elements of both language and literacy instruction, students will be unable to meet their full communication potential (Geist, Erickson, Hatch, Erwin-Davidson, & Dorney, 2017). Unfortunately, for certain students with disabilities, they may have limited opportunity to fully engage in emergent literacy learning (Erickson, Hatton, Roy, Fox, & Renne 2007).

Comprehensive literacy instruction must begin early and be done often and incorporated into daily classroom routines. Every opportunity must be taken to foster a child's development of symbolic communication. Language and literacy learning cannot exist separately, and both directly affect a child's future total communication skills for academic and life success. If teachers do not seek evidence-based strategies to fully engage their students with significant cognitive and communication disabilities in comprehensive literacy instruction, then these students are also losing opportunities to fully develop their total communication skills. Learning

to be literate is vitally important for all children with CCN so they can participate more fully in society. Spoken and written communication is a human right, not a privilege.

Writing is one form of communication and Aided Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) systems are another form of communication that may be the only way students with CCN can access alphabet letters and learn to spell words. Learning to spell and learning to decode words for writing and reading allows a person unlimited expression. That said, educators need to know how to instruct children who use AAC to read and write. Most educators are aware that language is needed for students to learn, but the language for daily learning may only be available or accessible on a student's aided AAC system. AAC systems include a range of aided language tools, from no-tech, paper-based systems, to higher-tech speech-generating devices, but all systems should give students access to frequently used and highly useful words (core vocabulary) along with alphabet letters for daily communication and literacy learning.

It is imperative that students with complex communication needs make significant progress on their reading and writing skills before they graduate from high school on or before age 22. However, evidence suggests that teachers still report confusion about how to provide explicit instruction to students with disabilities (Stockard, Wood, Coughlin, & Khoury, 2018) and how to measure student learning outcomes when the students have significant and complex learning and communication needs. For example, findings from one study (Stahmer, Oliver, Schetter, & Stanford University, PACE, 2020) suggested that despite teachers having been trained to implement EBPs, the teachers were not generalizing the presented skills to the classroom. In fact, results indicated that less than 80% of the skills being implemented were done correctly.

For example, (Erwin-Davidson, personal communication, August 22, 2022), reported that emerging evidence from a community-engaged longitudinal study focused on discovering what happens when a school district implements a comprehensive literacy curriculum suggests that even with explicit instructional lesson guidelines provided in a teacher's guide, not all special educators even at year two of implementation, feel either confident or skilled when teaching their students with CCN to read and write.

The central aim of this study is to compare and contrast 4.6 hours of video-recorded instructional discourse collected from three experienced special education teachers of self-contained classrooms serving beginning communicators and early literacy learners during initial months of the class-wide delivery of an evidence-based comprehensive literacy curriculum (Readtopia).

Methods

Participants

A total of 68 participants were consented to this study. The participants included 53 middle and high school students ranging in age from 13-22, three special education teachers (SETs), three speech-language pathologists (SLPs) and nine instructional assistants (IAs) with a range of instructional experience and education. The classrooms under study were situated in a large urban school district in southern California. The classroom demographics were consistent with the district's racial, socioeconomic, and cultural demographic breakdown as follows: 43 percent of students were identified as Hispanic, 32 percent White, 16 percent Asian-Pacific, and 1 percent identified as African-American. In addition, 13 percent of students were classified as English Language learners, and 38 percent were identified as socioeconomically disadvantaged.

Racial Demographics

SocioEconomic Status

Speech-Language Pathologists (SLPs)

The three participating SLPs were licensed, certified, and credentialed for school-age instruction. The three SLPs who assisted students in the classrooms under this study had at least five years of practice in a school.

Special Education Teachers (SETs)

The participating special education teachers had five or more years of teaching experience and held both a master's degree and special education teaching credentials.

Students

The attending speech-language pathologist reported that each student was placed in a more educationally restricted self-contained/alternative classrooms because each student was found eligible for an individualized educational program plan (IEP). Specifically, each student scored below the 1st percentile on most of the required standardized assessments and presented with significant learning and language disabilities that required a smaller teacher-student ratio and differentiated instruction. Of relevance to this study, many of the students in the classrooms were described as “nonverbal”, in addition to presenting with unknown or undefined levels of reading or writing skill.

As part of the overarching study implementing a three-pronged language and literacy intervention, each teacher and SLP who served the consented classrooms, were required to be assess their students at the beginning of the school year on communication and literacy skills. For the purposes of initiating a standardized way to track and measure progress in communication since onset of intervention, the Communication Matrix (CM) profile (Rowland, 2004) was completed for most students. The CM is a structured observational assessment tool

designed to document and track expressive communication progress of children who have severe or multiple disabilities, including children with sensory, motor and cognitive impairments.

The highest communication levels for the 53 students enrolled in the consented classrooms ranged from Level III (presymbolic, unconventional communication) to Level VII+ (students using early symbolic communication/language combining two-three words using spontaneous speech, to more conventional communication, combining four or five words using spontaneous speech with a mean length of utterance of 4-5 morphemes). Teachers were informed that any student who only imitated speech, or would not speak unless prompted, was not considered a conventional communicator, but a presymbolic communicator, and should be assessed on the CM.

In addition, the classroom teachers screened each consented student in their classroom using the piloted Readtopia Reading Placement Tool at the beginning of the school year (BOY), and before video recordings were conducted in the classroom. Therefore, at time of the scheduled video recordings, students' reading levels ranged from Emergent Level 1 (preschool grade-level equivalence) to Conventional Level 5 (grade 2.0-2.5 equivalence).

Procedures

Data Collection

Video recordings of Readtopia instruction were required as part of the overall pilot study, but teachers scheduled these visits according to their comfort, confidence, and work-related scheduling commitments. Video recordings were scheduled for 30 to 45 minutes during Readtopia instruction and recorded using researcher-approved and unintrusive Smart Phones. Consents to be recorded were checked by research assistants, and video recordings captured verbal and nonverbal communication between consented teacher and students. Participant names,

school names, and specific locations were deidentified. A total of four hours and 37 minutes of Readtopia instruction were gathered.

Data Analysis

Codes. The different areas of the video recordings that coders were tracking were teacher questions, student responses, and AAC modeling. For each teacher question, the question was broken into a transcription of the question, how many times the question was asked in succession, and what kind of question was asked (open or closed). Student responses were tracked for which questions students responded to and how the student responded (bodily response, verbal response, AAC response, Aide response, or no response), and if the student responded verbally or with AAC the response was transcribed. When looking at modeling coders were tracking how many words teachers were modeling while asking questions and how many words they could have modeled while asking questions.

Video Watching. The primary investigator watched each video once without taking notes just to analyze and get a sense of the instructional setting, instructional style, and communication expectations. Then each video was analyzed again while notes were taken about the classroom climate and how teachers and students were interacting. Then, repeated discourse analysis took place until data saturation was reached for each individual video transcription.

The discourse from video recordings were transcribed using intelligent transcription. This type of transcription means each coder transcribed every word that teachers were saying but excluded pauses, status, and filler words and to capture the meaning of the sentence without a focus on grammatical correctness or fluent expression.

Analysis of Discourse. Discourse was analyzed by the primary investigator through comparing teacher questions, teacher modeling of questions, and student responses. Each aspect

of teacher questions was taken and compared to how many student responses were received and how those students were responding. Teacher modeling while asking questions was compared against the how many times students used AAC to respond. These comparisons were turned into ratios and percentages to see across the classrooms how these different variables were affecting student language and responses.

Constant Comparison. Through constant comparison of teacher-to-student communication exchanges within and between classrooms raw codes were then categorized, and main concepts of identified to make sense of the transcribed textual data (Lichtman, 2013). Each video was then watched no less than two times but no more than six times, by two novice coders at separate times, with no communication as coding took place. to track and document all codes.

A constant comparison on discourse across these classrooms. The agreed-upon data was then analyzed by the primary investigator to remove prompts that were originally coded as questions. A descriptive analysis using both QUANT & QUAL approaches helped make sense of the textual data. Categories of meaning were identified revealing both barriers and supports to teacher-student discourse during class wide instruction.

Data Saturation. Data saturation was reached when enough categorical information was obtained and no further coding was feasible (Fusch & Ness, 2015). Thus, when no additional or new information was attained, all codes were collected, combined, and organized by the primary investigator onto one Excel document. All codes were then independently reviewed by two novice coders and one experienced coder without discussion. During this independent coding, each line of verbatim discourse was analyzed for questions types, teacher modeling, and how students were responding. Discourse was also compared to Readtopia teacher guide to see if the teachers were following the curriculum as recommended.

Intercoder Reliability

Each video was individually viewed and coded by two novice coders, and one experienced coder, with a total of three coders viewing the videos and the consequent transcriptions. Each coder viewed them independently without communicating with the other coders or checking their findings. After combining the codes onto one document, the two coders for each video met with an experienced researcher to dissect and confirm codes. Consensus was sought on defining the types of questions, the number of questions, and the number of missed opportunities to model language naturally. The consensus was also sought around the interpretation of classroom climate, teachers' instructional actions, and student-teacher communication in the classrooms. At the initial pass, intercoder reliability between three different coders was 79% agreement, then through consensus, the coders reached 100% agreement.

Results

The following concepts of meaning were identified during Readtopia instructional time and then compared across classrooms from 4.6 hours of verbatim transcribed videorecorded classroom communication.

Teacher's Lack of Modeling

Teacher's opportunities to model core words were tracked by counting any of the 36 UC words that could have been modeled while the teacher was asking a question. Teacher one had 145 opportunities, teacher two had 375 opportunities, and teacher three had 285 opportunities to model core words. Across classrooms there were a total of 805 opportunities the teachers could have modeled the most salient core words during instruction (including question words who, what, where, when) they only modeled core words 63 times.

While having these opportunities to model teachers were modeling at a rate of once for every 21 opportunities across classrooms. Teacher one modeled a total of four words, teacher two modeled a total of 59 words, and teacher three modeled zero words across all classroom instruction. There was a total of 37 words modeled across all videorecorded classroom instruction.

Across classrooms there was an average of 9.35 opportunities to modeled for every one word that teachers modeled. Teacher one had an average of 38.5 opportunities asked for every one word that was modeled, teacher two had an average of 4.2 opportunities asked for every one word that was modeled, teacher three had no words modeled.

Table. 1 Teacher Modeling

	Example:	Teacher 1	Teacher 2	Teacher 3	Combined Teacher Totals:
# Teacher Opportunities to Model Core Words	Any of the 36 UC words that could have been modeled when asking questions	145	375	285	805
# Teacher Actually Modeling Core Words	Question: "What do you have?" Modeled: "what, do, have" Count: 3 words modeled	4	59	0	63
# Of Unique Questions Teacher Modeled	Question: "What did you eat this morning?" Modeled: "what, you" Count: 1 question modeled	4	33	0	37

Limited Wait Time

There was a total of 277 minutes of video recordings across classrooms. Teacher one had two videos totaling 77 minutes, teacher two had two videos totaling 90 minutes, and teacher three had five videos totaling 110 minutes of classroom instruction.

Across all 277 minutes of video recordings there were a total of 589 questions asked by a teacher to the students in the special day classrooms. Teacher one asked 154 questions, teacher 2 asked 248 questions, and teacher three asked 187 questions.

Across all classrooms there was an average of 2.13 questions asked per minute. Teacher one had an average of two questions per minute, teacher two asks an average of 2.75 questions per minute, and teacher three asks an average of 1.7 questions per minute.

Given that the average number of questions asked per minute is 2.13 this gives an average time of 28 seconds for a student to process the question, look at their aided language system, decide on what words to use, find the words to respond, select words or utterances, and then respond. Teacher one had an average of 30 seconds of wait time, teacher two had an average of 22 seconds of wait time, and teacher three had an average of 35 seconds of wait time.

Teacher Repetition of Questions

There were a total number of 589 questions asked across classrooms. These were the amount of questions asked by a teacher in the classroom, and some of these were repeated verbatim to the same student or different students. There was also the case that teachers would devolve their questions from open-ended questions, to close-ended questions, to prompts. This devolving of questions goes from requiring questions to have multi-word responses, to single word responses, to a fill-in-the-blank answer. This devolving of questions was not counted as a repeated question but should be considered when thinking about repeated questions.

Across all three classrooms there were a total of 401 repeated questions. Teacher one asked 147 repeated questions, teacher two asked 126 repeated questions, and teacher three asked 121 repeated questions. On average for every 1.47 questions asked there was one question repeated. Teacher one repeated a question for every 1.05 questions asked, teacher two repeated a question for every 1.97 questions asked, and teacher three repeated a question for every 1.55 questions asked.

Teacher's Reliance on Closed Questions

Questions asked by teachers during classroom instruction were separated into open-ended and closed-ended questions. Open-ended questions were defined as questions that require a unique multi-word response, and closed-ended questions were defined as questions that had a predetermined one word or yes/no response.

Closed-ended questions were asked a total of 451 times across all classroom video recordings. Teacher one asked 106 closed-ended questions, teacher two asked 187 closed-ended questions, and teacher three asked 158 closed-ended questions.

Open-ended questions were asked a total of 138 times across all classroom video recordings. Teacher one asked 48 open-ended questions, teacher two asked 61 open-ended questions, teacher three asked 29 open-ended questions.

On average across all three classrooms there was 3.27 closed-ended questions asked for every one open-ended question asked. Teacher one asked an average of 2.2 closed-ended questions asked for every one open-ended question, teacher two asked an average of 3.1 closed-ended questions asked for every one open-ended question, and teacher three asked an average of 5.5 closed-ended questions asked for every one open-ended question.

Across classrooms repeated questions were asked anywhere from two to 15 times in succession. Teacher one asked repeated questions two to 15 times in succession, teacher two asked repeated questions two to six times in succession, and teacher three asked repeated questions two to seven times in succession.

Table. 2 Teacher Questions

	Example:	Teacher 1	Teacher 2	Teacher 3	Combined Teacher Totals:
Total number of Teacher Questions (Open + Closed)	Any questions asked by a teacher during instructional time	154	248	187	589
# Open Questions (must combine words to answer questions)	“What can we learn about the ancient Mayan people by studying their cities?”	48	61	29	138
# Closed Questions (requires only one word to respond)	“Do you think that they have that technology?”	106	187	158	451
# Questions Repeated	The number of questions that were repeated in succession after the original question was asked	147	126	128	401
# Of Times Repeated	The range of times that a question was asked in succession	2 to 15	2 to 6	2 to 7	2 to 15

Limited Use of Aided Language Input

Use of aided language input by teachers in the classroom was measured by how many total questions were modeled by the teacher while asking questions. There was a total of 63 instances where a teacher modeled UC words while asking questions and this included repeated questions.

Across all three special day classrooms the teachers modeled UC question words during 38 unique questions. Teacher one modeled question words during four unique questions, teacher two modeled question words during 33 unique questions, and teacher three modeled question words during zero unique questions.

There was an average of 21.2 unique questions asked for every one unique question that was modeled by a teacher while asking questions across the classrooms. Teacher one had an average of 36.25 unique questions asked for every one unique questions that was modeled,

teacher two had an average of 11.4 unique questions asked for every one unique questions that was modeled, teacher three had no unique questions that were modeled.

Limited Opportunities for Student Responses

Student responses were categorized into bodily/physical responses (which could include a student moving their head, hands, or standing up), intelligible spoken word (which included anytime a student verbal spoke a word that was understood on the video recording), device generated response (which include a student selecting a response on a AAC device or UC board), no student response, or aide response (which is when a student's aide would manually select a response on the student's AAC, or if the aide verbally responded to the teacher for the student). Multiple student responses could be counted for each question because multiple students could respond to a single question.

Across classrooms there were a total of 281 student responses which were specifically 49 bodily responses, 237 spoken responses, 15 device generated responses, 56 no student responses, and seven aide responses. Teacher one had a total of 47 responses across 154 questions asked that included 17 bodily responses, 36 spoken responses, 5 device generated responses, 3 no student responses, and zero aide responses. Teacher two had a total of 135 responses across 248 questions asked that included 30 bodily responses, 107 spoken responses, 10 device generated responses, 39 no student responses, and four aide responses. Teacher three had a total of 99 responses across 187 questions asked that included two bodily responses, 94 spoken responses, zero device generated responses, 14 no student responses, and three aide responses.

Table. 3 Student Responses

	Example:	Teacher 1	Teacher 2	Teacher 3	Combined Teacher Totals:
Total number of Student Responses	Any time a student responded to a teacher question in any way	47	135	99	281
Body/Physical Response	Nodding/shaking head, thumbs up/down, physical movements	17	30	2	49
Intelligible Spoken Word	Any verbal words that a student spoke	36	107	94	237
Device Generated Response	Selecting a response on a device or UC Core Board	5	10	0	15
No Student Response	Student did not respond to teacher question in any way	3	39	14	56
Aide responded for Student	Aide selected a response or verbally communicated an answer for the student	0	4	3	7

Discussion

In sum, the discourse analysis revealed five primary barriers to the transactional model of communication in these three special day classrooms. The barriers in these classrooms revolved around the teacher's ability to model core words to students and the types and way they were asking questions. The Readtopia teacher guide did have strategies and implementation techniques that were developed to minimize these issues across classrooms.

Teachers were not taking advantage of the numerous opportunities that were available to model core words while asking questions. Despite having a total of 805 opportunities across the classrooms the teachers on took advantage of modeling on 63 occasions. This could potentially inhibit a student's ability to learn on their own AAC and continue learning and developing their communication skills. Teachers were only modeling 16.8 percent of the opportunities that were available while asking questions in the classroom.

While teachers were asking questions they were asking on average two questions per minute, allowing 30 seconds of wait time before they moved on to another student or asked another question. This did not include when teachers asked the same question repeatedly and in succession. This could leave significantly less time for students to answer when students have to process the question and then go through the process of figuring out their answer and then attempting to respond on their AAC device. Teacher two had the lowest average wait time of 22 seconds which means they were asking almost three questions per minute for students to respond to. By providing more wait time student can potentially respond more frequently and with more intentional communication.

Teachers had a tendency to repeat their questions either while asking the class a question or they would ask multiple students in the class the same question. This led to 68 percent of all questions asked by a teacher being a repeated question. By asking the same question repeatedly it can potentially not require all students to respond and can lead to them not being actively engaged in responding or communicating.

Throughout all of the questions teachers asked during instruction the majority of questions were closed-ended questions that only required a yes/no, one word, or predetermined response. These questions were being asked instead of open-ended questions that require multi-word or unique responses. By having 76 percent of all questions asked be closed-ended questions it does not require students to learn how to combine words to communicate with teachers or other individuals and can inhibit the ability to participate in dialogue and contribute to a conversation.

Teachers' modeled a total of 63 times while asking questions, but only modeled during 33 unique questions. When teachers' were modeling they would model for the same question or

would model the same one word while asking the question multiple times. Being able to model equally across questions asked can potentially help students how to combine and use all 36 UC words to communicate in and out of the classroom.

Despite these classrooms having students with complex communication needs the majority of student responses to questions were verbal responses. Only two percent of all responses were device generated responses and 20 percent of all questions asked had no student response at all. Students in classrooms that had the most modeling done by the teacher were also the classrooms that had the most device generated responses, when the teacher had no modeling in the classroom there were also no device generated responses.

Limitations

Limitations of this study include the video recordings only took place during invited Readtopia lessons when teachers felt most prepared to be recorded; video recordings were not conducted randomly. Data coding could only be analyzed from numerous repeated viewings of what coders could see and hear but does not necessarily represent what happened on days that were not recorded. The three coders involved in the study were novice coders and have little to no experience coding video recordings. Teachers were only in a six to nine month time frame of adopting Readtopia as part of their daily instructional routine and were still transitioning from their typical style of teaching to recommended Readtopia instructional style.

True discourse analysis was challenging, given that “discourse” is an interchange of ideas, thoughts, and comments that is transactional in nature. There was little evidence of true discourse, or a balanced exchange of information between teachers and students, even with the newly added aided language supports. Despite having access to the Readtopia teacher’s guide that suggested different ways teachers could invite participation and encourage comments,

teachers instead continued to rely heavily on a traditional and comfortable pattern of teacher-led Q & A.

Implications

After analysis of barriers to transactional classroom interactions the primary investigator identified the primary supports that teachers and Speech-Language Pathologists (SLPs) could provide in the classroom for their students with complex communication needs. Teachers and SLPs could collaborate on ways to increase opportunities for aided language users to naturally comment and ask questions during class-wide Readtopia instruction. For example, if SLPs were in the classroom during Readtopia instruction SLPs could help remind teachers to give students additional time to process and respond to questions. SLPs could coach teachers and aides on how to model comments and questions using core vocabulary as necessary aided language input.

Teachers could insert scripted comments in the Readtopia guide to remind themselves to encourage students to contribute original comments, give an opinion, or ask a question. Teachers could ask instructional aides to help students find question words on their aided language systems, and teach the students when to ask questions, and what question words to use. Teachers could insert reminders in the Readtopia guide to ask more open-ended questions that would encourage students to combine two or more words for increased opportunities to use newly learned vocabulary expand their response. Teachers could create their own script as a reminder on how to reword questions without resorting to question over-simplification or devolving to fill-in-the-blank questions. These types of supports would move teachers and students to a more transactional model of communication.

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